

Militancy in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: It's Political Impact On District Charsadda (2007 to 2017)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 15,2025</p> <p>Accepted: July 17,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Militancy, Terrorism, Extremism, Al-Qaida, Afghanistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16041503</p>	<p><i>The post 9/11 immense wave of militancy has affected the lives and standard of living of common people across the country, especially in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Such menace gave birth to numerous apprehensions and affected lives subject masses and adversely impacted the institutions. The current research work attempts to investigate the political impact of militancy on Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province with a case study of district Charsadda (2007 to 2017). This research focuses on period 2007-2017 because the militancy became more visible in the form of suicide attacks in Charsadda in 2007. Although it existed earlier also, but increased manifold during this period because of the lawlessness, extremism and terrorism. As a result of 9/11 attacks, the United States started "Operation Enduring Freedom" against the key leaders of Al Qaeda in Afghanistan. Due to the close proximity and porous Pak-Afghan border, the militants infiltrated into erstwhile Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) of Pakistan making FATA a safe sanctuary for themselves. This militancy did not remain confined to FATA, but also spilled over into the mainland Pakistan, especially to the adjacent Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Charsadda, being adjacent to the erstwhile Mohmand Agency, suffered the most. It was mainly targeted, because, the key political figures of this area have different ideology, as opposed to the militants. In this paper, the impact of militancy on politics especially two influential parties i.e. Awami National Party (ANP) and Quami Watan Party (QWP) has been taken into consideration. The policies of these parties were against the militants. Moreover, these parties remained in power and harmed the ongoing insurgency. Resultantly, they were targeted.</i></p>

Introduction

This research work discusses the emergence of militancy in district Charsadda and argues that militancy is not indigenous here, rather spilled over from Kunar province of Afghanistan via Mohmand Agency, now a settled district. It also assesses political impacts of militancy on district Charsadda. The time period, 2007-2017 is the focus of current research because the militancy started in the form of suicide attacks in Charsadda since 2007.

Since its independence, Pakistan and Afghanistan have been having tense relations because of the issue of Durand line (Rizvi, 1971, p. 143). The Durand line is a border between Pakistan and Afghanistan. Afghanistan does not recognize it as permanent international border. It is interspersed with high passes and mountains that historically remained route for invasions and trade, between Central, South Asia and the current Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. On both sides of the border, live various Pashtun ethnic tribes. (Hayat, 2000, p. xvii).

The region came to the limelight when the former Soviet Union invaded Afghanistan in December 1979 to salvage the embattled Communist Afghan regime. The resistance against Russian was planned, organized, and launched from Pakistan. The US, Muslim world and other states supported the resistance making the tribal areas of Pakistan as a base camp for Jihad (Abbas, 2010).

After the Soviet withdrawal from Afghanistan, under Geneva Accords, a power struggle started among different factions of Afghan *Mujahideen*. The seven years long civil war, created an environment for a new religious Pakhtun ethnic group, named Taliban.

In 1996, by defeating the splinter groups of *Mujahideen*, the Taliban captured most of the Pakhtun populated areas including the capital Kabul and declared Afghanistan as Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan. They also declared Mullah Muhammad Umar as *Amir-ul-Momeneen*. (The Chief of the believers). Taliban's introduced strict form of *Shariah* laws. Their coming to power ignited the spirit of *Jihad* in Muslims all over the world. Needless to say, that *jihad* was against the West. Hence Afghanistan turned into a hub of militant groups carrying out clandestine activities against the West including the US. In the year 1998, US embassies in Kenya and Tanzania were attacked. The US held *Al-Qaida* responsible for those attacks. (Library, 2018). Then America put the whole blame of the 9/11 attacks on *Al-Qaida* and that incident proved to be a turning point

that initiated the Global War on Terrorism (GWOt). The US was of the firm view that the attacks were carried out by *Al-Qaida* based in Afghanistan". (Hussain, 2005, p. 15). Before taking an action, the US asked Pakistan to provide logistic support. The US administration made it clear to Pakistan that "either you are with us or against us". (Amin, 2014, p. 1). The military ruler of Pakistan General Pervez Musharraf joined the Global War on Terrorism (GWOt) and supported the US action in Afghanistan. He provided air bases to US-led forces and allowed supply through Pakistan territories. On Pakistan side, the armed religious groups opposed Musharraf's Afghan policy and started insurgency in the tribal areas (Rohan and Iqbal, 2011).

In the settled area of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the Malakand division adjacent to district Charsadda resorted to arm struggle against Musharraf. A pro-Taliban organization *Tanzeem Nifaz-i-Shariat-i-Mohammadi* (TNSM) led by Sufi Mohammad, called for introduction of *Sharia*. The Provincial Government of Awami National Party (ANP) endorsed the demands of Sufi Mohammad but later, the insurgency in the said area took another shift. The militant organization deviated from their demands and challenged the writ of the state. The Government therefore, started operation in Malakand division in 2009 to reinstate the state writ in the region. Due to the military operation, the internally displaced persons (IDPs) moved to different surrounding regions particularly Charsadda (Tiedemann, 2012, pp. 345-46). It can be stated that the spillover effect, following the military operations, seriously affected Charsadda through Mohmand Agency and Malakand, as reportedly militants entered Charsadda in the disguise of IDPs.

Charsadda is located in the centre of the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Mardan is in its East, Nowshera to its South East, Peshawar to its South, Mohmand in its West and Malakand is lying in the north of the district (Gul, 2008 p.5). Until 1988, Charsadda remained part of Peshawar district, when the then Governor Lieutenant General Fazale Haq raised it a status to a separate District (Munir, 2012, p. 179). It has an area of 996 km² with population of 1.616 million, with a literacy rate of forty three per cent (Smeda, 2018).

The people of district Charsadda, Mohmand and Malakand have frequent interaction with each other. The links provided an opportunity to militants to infiltrate into Charsadda. Furthermore, Mohmand Agency has a common border with the two provinces of Afghanistan i.e. Nangarhar and Kunar. The insurgency in Afghanistan always impacted Mohmand Agency including the peace of Charsadda, because of the deteriorating law and order situation, aided by war on terror. Militants frequently attacked schools, mosques, civilians and para-military personnel to create fear. The terrorist attack on Qawmi Watan Party (QWP) Chairperson Aftab Ahmad Khan Sherpao in Charsadda in April 2007 in a public gathering followed by second attack on him during Eid prayers the same year, further intensified militancy in Charsadda (Babakhel, 2016).

Literature Review

A bulk of literature was produced on the rise of militancy after 9/11 in Pakistan explaining its roots, causes and its effects on Pakistani society. Gunaratna and Iqbal explain the spillover of militancy from Afghanistan into ex-FATA of Pakistan and argue that operation "Enduring Freedom" forced the insurgent groups to flee from Afghanistan to the tribal areas of Pakistan. The authors further elaborate that the erstwhile FATA proved to be the safe haven of these insurgent groups from where they used to launch terrorist attacks across Pakistan. They argue that Musharraf decision to ally with US against its GWOt, turned once "blue eyed" assets into enemies of Pakistan shifting insurgency to the settled areas of Pakistan. (Rohan and Iqbal, 2011)

Rahman is of the view that Musharraf support for US war in Afghanistan, distorted the image of Pakistani establishment, igniting the desires of foreign elements as well as local militants to start militarize campaign against Musharraf Government. The authors are also of the view that assassination attempt on General Musharraf and terrorist plots of attacking London and Barcelona were launched from Bajaur Agency (Ullah, 2012).

He further argues that the US diversion of enough resources to Iraq and the inability of Pakistani forces to overcome the crises in the region, gave enough space to insurgent elements to reorganize themselves strategically and tactfully in the form of Tehreek Taliban Pakistan (TTP) in 2007.

Naseer elaborated that the mechanism through which the local criminals and militants groups were carrying out underground activities in FATA and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are for earning money. (Naseer, 2017)

Hussain termed that Pakistan's relations with Afghanistan, to an extent are inclined by historical legacy before 1947 Afghanistan and British India relations. He explored as to how Pakistan Army engagement with the Afghan Islamists coupled with Pakistani establishment after Cold War. The post-Cold War agenda of Pakistan was well embraced by Afghan Islamist. (Hussain R. , 2005)

Various scholars have covered a range of topics regarding militancy in the Af-Pak region, its origin, rise and cross border movement of militants. However there is no comprehensive study was conducted which could explain the spillover of militancy to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa from Afghanistan especially its political impact on district Charsadda. It was due to that research gap, that the current study was undertaken.

Problem Statement

Pakhtun tribes residing along either side of the Durand Line in Af-Pak region hold close blood relations and have been interacting with each other since time immemorial. The nexus that developed between militant organizations of Afghanistan and Pakistan during 1980s, revived rather further increased the ties, ushering a new era of militancy in FATA. Militants attacked innocent citizens, law enforcement agencies, destroyed schools, carried out bomb blasts, damaged social and political environment causing huge loss to economy and human security in Pakistan, as for as Charsadda is concerned, it was affected badly due to its close proximity to erstwhile Mohmand Agency and Malakand. The study investigates how this militancy spilled over from Afghanistan to ex-FATA and then to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa with a focus on Charsadda.

Methodology

This research is descriptive and analytical in nature that includes both present and historical information on the subject matter and is based on the analysis derived from primary and secondary qualitative data. For this purpose data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The secondary data was collected from books, journals, reports and other relevant published documents. The primary data was collected through interview schedule from experts, government officials, politicians and affected families. The respondents (sample) for these interviews was collected through purposive sampling techniques- a non-probability sample, which is selected based on that features of the population to achieve the objectives of the study. Primary data was collected through interview schedule. The interview schedule was finalized after the review of relevant literature.

Political impact of militancy on district Charsadda

Militancy has deep rooted impact on the state affairs on regional and inter-regional level. The insurgents and militants damaged the social, political, economic, educational infrastructure in Pakistan especially in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. They severely disturbed the political balance in the country while unleashing attacks on the people affiliated with political parties (Bari, 2019).

The terror and violent campaign by the militant groups resulted in decline in the activities of political parties in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa particularly in Charsadda. The militants specifically, targeted Charsadda which is considered to be the base camps of the nationalist parties. The militants groups also attacked women who were engaged with political parties. On the whole, the militancy severely weakened the federation of Pakistan because of Pakistan's decision of joining the US war on terror. The chain of extremism and terrorism created distrust among the state and its citizens. Some of the people argued that Pakistan's security establishment was directly or indirectly supporting the militant and insurgent groups (Irshad, 2011).

The above discussion reflects that the war on terror devastated Pakistan in terms of politics and economics. In 2001, the Taliban rule ended as result of the US attacks on Afghanistan. Immediately, Northern Alliance formed government in Kabul that started work against Pakistan on India's behalf. With the prior consensus of the Afghan government, India opened consulates on the Pak-Afghan border region that were potential threat to Pakistan's security. Reportedly, more than thirty consulates have been established by the India in the region.

The resultant situation was utilized by India in its favor in three ways. First, India declared the freedom fighters in Jammu and Kashmir as terrorists and militants. Second, it approached different countries such as US for civil nuclear energy. Third, Indian developed friendly relations with the Afghan regime and in this way it increased its role and influence in Afghanistan. Above all, Pakistanis was forced to be in diplomatic isolation. On India's behalf the US Congress passed several bills which systematically affected Pakistan's interest (Javed, 2011).

During the 2007-17, the wave of violence in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and FATA adopted a new course of target killing-viz-targeting barbers, singers, actors and the owners of video shops on the ground that their professions were un-Islamic (Ahmad, 2009). The pro-government elements and the Pakhtun elders were killed. According to a rough estimate about 1200 elders or tribal *maliks* were killed by Taliban because of their support for the government (Ashraf, 2010).

Moreover, the political parties' activists and leaders in Charsadda were on their hit list. Aftab Ahmed Khan Sherpao and Asfandiyar Wali Khan were fortunate to escape these suicide attacks. Nevertheless, several members of the Provincial Assembly from Charsadda were killed. (Saddiqui, 2010). The Awami National Party (ANP), having electoral strength in the area, also suffered a lot in district Charsadda. Its leader Asfandiyar Wali Khan was targeted along with other candidates during their election campaign. He escaped narrowly but many of his workers were killed and injured during these attacks in Charsadda.

Political History of District Charsadda

Charsadda is historically known as the base camp of politicians. It has produced influential political figure such as Bacha Khan, Dr Khan Sahib, Abdul Wali Khan, Hayat Muhammad Khan Sherpao, Begum Nasim Wali Khan, Sardar Ali Khan, Nisar Muhammad Khan. Aftab Ahmad Khan Sherpao and Asfandiyar Wali Khan, who have left significant mark on the political and social landscape of the region, apart from the above mentioned influential socio-political personalities, some religious personalities such a Sahib Turangzai, Haji Muhammad Amin, Shamsul Haq Afghani, Mulana Muhammad Munir and Maulana Hassan Jan also rendered services in terms of religious comprehension.

The above mentioned political and religious figures have deep rooted impact on the Charsadda's political history. The people of this region are very democratic and politically conscious. They are also strict adherents to Islam and *Pakhtunwali*.

ANP Under Attack

ANP has always been critical of Pakistan's Afghan policy especially its support for *Jihad*. Its leader Wali Khan termed Afghan *Jihad* as *Fasad* (destruction). In his view Pakistan would face the repercussions of interference in the other affairs other countries. On the other hand, ANP was supporting Russia, Communism and Secularism. The ANP leadership always ridiculed religious people and blamed them for making money in the name of *Jihad*. The *militant* organizations, therefore, targeted ANP and its leadership. (Khan, 2019).

In 2008 general elections, ANP came into power in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province with the support of Pakistan People's Party. Both the parties formed coalition government in the province. Initially, ANP did not own the anti-Taliban perspective vocally. Rather, it practiced an appeasing policy. With the passage of time, however, this point of view changed and it supported military operation against the militants. Resultantly, ANP became the prime target of the insurgents (Islam, 2019).

ANP leaders started public condemnation of the militants. Asfandiyar Wali Khan's statements regarding the militants completely changed the party's stance on militancy. He argued that the Taliban were terrorists who were targeting innocent people. He stressed upon the state to adopt uniform policy regarding elimination of terrorism. He argued that no group or faction of Taliban was entitled to have blue eyed status. All of them were terrorists and were to be treated accordingly. The menace of terrorism had reached to the roots of the country and any miscalculation and delay at this level would cause irreparable loss to the nation (Report, 2019). Similarly, the ANP General Secretary (central) Mian Iftikhar Hussain whose only son was killed in a militant attack further reinforced the party's position against the militants. He advocated peace and was very vocal against the Taliban (Report, 2019).

Although, the ANP leader Asfandiyar Wali Khan also supported the peace talks with the Taliban that began during the early days of Nawaz Sharif's third term of government. He, however, supported the talks on the condition that Taliban should accept the government writ and thereby put down their weapons. Accordingly to facilitate peace talk, he argued that the failure of the talks need to be followed by a military operation just like their government did in Swat and Malakand in May 2009 (News, 2019).

The TTP took serious note of the ANP anti-*Jihad* stance. According to them the war was not against terrorism but was basically a war between secularism and Islam. They considered that in that battle the ANP was fighting to establish a secular system, while the Taliban were endeavoring to enforce Islamic laws. Moreover, as a secular political entity, the ANP was fighting an ideological war against the TTP since it came to power in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The TTP which advocated the political philosophy of Islam, had declared the ANP as its enemy. They argued that ANP being a secular political party necessarily contradicts their Islamist stance. The ideological differences watered the seeds of the conflict between the two rivals which brought destruction (Editor, 2019).

ANP was the most targeted party as hundreds of its workers were killed and injured in bomb blasts and target killing since 2009. It may be noted that this party was in government in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa at that time. Besides, the party lost three MPAs, including Senior Minister Bashir Ahmed Bilour, in the subsequent attacks (Salman, 2012, p. 246).

A number of attacks were made on party leaders in Charsadda. Its party leader Asfandiyar Wali Khan was targeted in October 2008 in his residence (Hujra) when he was exchanging Eid greetings with party workers. Although he remained unhurt in the attack but four people were killed including his personal guard. Several others notables were injured on the occasion. In another bomb attack in February 2008, at a pre-election rally in Nahkai Shabqadar, district Charsadda, over 25 people lost their lives (Faiz, 2019).

In April 2013, in Katozai Shabqar, district Charsadda, ANP PK-21 candidate, Syed Masoom Shah was targeted during his election campaign with a remote-controlled device. Luckily, he survived with a minor injury but other party workers received fatal injuries including his driver (News, 2019). In the same month another ANP candidate Ahmad Khan from Charsadda PK-17 was targeted in Sardheri bazar during his election campaign. The bomb was planted on bicycle near his election office. The candidate survived but one person was killed and 12 people were injured in the attack (Shah, 2019).

These attacks proved to be a catastrophic for the ANP in the 2013 elections in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in general and Charsadda district in particular. ANP secured only one National Assembly and five Provincial Assembly seats. Charsadda is considered the stronghold of ANP in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. It is the native land of ANP head Asfandiyar Wali Khan, but unexpectedly there was lower performance in this district. The party could not secure even a single seat in this district (Dawn News, 2019). Asfandiyar Wali Khan contested election from NA-7 Charsadda and was defeated by Maulana Gouhar Shah of (JUI-F) by a huge margin of fifteen thousand votes. Even PTI candidate got more votes than him (Editor, 2019). There must be some other reasons for that defeat but ANP attributed weak electoral performance to the sabotage activities in its electioneering

campaign. Earlier, in the 2008 elections, ANP had secured 48 seats in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Assembly and ten National Assembly seats.

There are different views of the different respondents about this failure of ANP in district Charsadda. According to a respondent, the main reason behind the failure of ANP in 2013 election in Charsadda was mainly due to militancy. The people were terrified by the terrorist attacks on the different candidates; hence party workers were not coming out of homes for the election campaign. Resultantly the party could not reach out to majority of the voters (Khan, 2019).

Another respondent argued that there were other reasons apart from militancy. In district Charsadda, Qawmi Watan Party (QWP) entered into an alliance with JUI-F for 2013 elections. Moreover, QWP got sympathy vote due to killing of one of its leader Alamzeb Umerzai by the militants. On the other hand, incumbency factor also played a role. ANP was in power and there were allegations of corruption against Charsadda leadership. Another important factor was Asfandyar Wali's leaving his native district after terrorist attack on him. To him, it was necessary for personal security but people did not accept his flight (Khan, 2019).

Qawmi Watan Party and militancy

Qawmi Watan Party (QWP) was the second largest political party after ANP in Charsadda district. Besides ANP, QWP was also affected by the wave of militancy. Aftab Ahmad Khan Sherpao was Charrperson of this party. In his political career, he remained on different portfolios in provincial and federal governments. During General Pervez Musharraf era, he was the interior minister during 2004-2007

He was frequently targeted by the militants in his home district Charsadda. The first bomb attack was carried out against him in Ktation korona locality of Charsadda city. The bomb blasted in his rally in 2007 in which 28 people were killed and 40 were injured. In the same year he was targeted again. He was offering Eid prayers with hundreds of worshipers near his residence in Sherpao. Although he survived but 57 people were killed on the spot and more than hundred were injured (QWP, 2019).

Apart from the above mention attacks, he was targeted for more than five times by the militants in district Charsadda but always remained safe. Aftab Sherpao being head of this political party remained the Interior Minister from 2004 to 2007. During that tenure, he took some punitive measures against the militants. So he was mostly targeted by the militants due to that role. Since Aftab Khan belonged to Charsadda, therefore the attacks on him were carried in that district. The Lal Masjid Islamabad operation 2007 was conducted during the minister ship of Aftab Khan, so he was the prime target of the militants. According to Umar Khalid, the Taliban Commander of Mohmand, that they targeted Aftab Sherpao because he cooperated with the armed forces in conducting the military operations in the tribal belt (Buneri, 2019). Some other militants, cited the Damadola Bajaur Madrassa incident to be one of reasons to target Aftab Khan.

Interestingly, Aftab Sherpao did not deny the targeting of Damadola Madrassa in Bajur. He said that "the attack on of Bajaur seminary was necessary as the militants were planning to conduct terrorist acts in different areas of the country". Similarly he justified operation against the militants at Lal Masjid and Jamia Hafsa (News, 2019). According to a respondent, the attacks on Aftab Sherpao are due his wrong policies. He wanted to please the US and West by targeting Islamists. One of the respondent said, that the attack on political figures were due to their ill-conceived policies and fighting someone else's war. The result was that the other side took revenge in the form of bomb blasts and target killing.

Conclusion

In October 2001, US started "Operation Enduring Freedom" against Taliban government especially the key leaders of Al Qaeda including Osama bin Laden in Afghanistan. Osama and his followers were held responsible for the 9/11 attack on Pentagon and World Trade Centre. Pakistan became significant ally of the US in that war against terror and thus remained the front line state throughout the war.

The tribal belt of Pakistan stretching along the Pak-Afghan border became hub of insurgency. The reason was that the belt had a proximity to the porous border. The same border provided an opportunity to Al Qaeda and Afghan Taliban to infiltrate into Pakistan. Al Qaeda and Afghan Taliban got stronger in terms of new alliance with like-minded persons from the ex-FATA and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Thus the Pakistani borderland became the hub of militancy and safe sanctuary for the militants.

This militancy did not confine only to the tribal areas, rather it spilled over to neighboring settled districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and other parts of Pakistan. The province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa was naturally the most affected province in Pakistan. It has paid a huge price in terms of human and other socio-economic losses.

How could the militants find safer places in the tribal belt of Pakistan? The reason was that Pakhtuns of the area led life in accordance *Pakhtunwali*. It is an unwritten code of life of Pakhtuns. Two principles of *Pakhtunwali* made the job of militants easy. The first principle was *Panahor* providing asylum to any one in trouble and coming into Pakhtun area. The second principle of *Pakhtunwali* was *Melmastia* or hospitality. Under the feature of *Melmastia*, Pakhtuns are bound to entertain guests to the best of their abilities and resources. By applying the

above attributes of *Pakhtunwali*, the local tribal people not only provided them sanctuaries but several of them gave the hands of their daughters and sisters in marriage to the militants.

Charsadda was targeted due to host of reasons. The district was attached to Mohmand tribal area and Malakand. Moreover, a highway connecting Mohmand and Bajur districts ends up in district Charsadda. Since Mohmand, Bajur and Malakand Division were strongholds of militancy, therefore they could easily sneak into Charsadda. Secondly two political parties i.e. Awami National Party (ANP) and Qaumi Watan Party (QWP) had their central head offices in Charsadda. These parties had harmed the militant groups one way or the other. So the militants decided to retaliate and target leaders and workers of both the parties.

The period from 2007 to 2017 was devastating in terms of sabotage activities in Charsadda. Militancy affected all spheres of life in the district. Like rest of the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, it paid a huge price socially, economically as well as politically. Hundreds of people lost their lives. However the political loss was enormous. Political activities and democratic norms flourish in a peaceful atmosphere. However, bomb blasts in public meetings and targeting political workers and leaders created a sense of disillusionment among the general masses. The general elections to the parliament and provincial assemblies scheduled for 2013 were marred by terrorism. The wave of terrorism not only terrified people to attend public meetings in the election campaign but also caused low turnout on polling day. Both ANP and QWP, having huge support in the district lost election in the district. Although defeat of both the parties had some other dynamics, but terrorism was certainly on top of the list.

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